

Health Issues in Rural Areas

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Abstract:

Health problems in India can be examined in various indicators as social, mental, physical, cultural, geographical, economical and personal. Health is crucial factor that put up to human wellbeing. Presently everybody in India face multitude of health problems. The study focuses on Health issues in rural area the study is conducted in Dabathuwa village. The purpose of the study is to understand socio- economic profile of the ill persons to understand about their health issues in rural area and to find out family duration of social relation in community and Illness Behavior & Wellbeing interview schedule method used to Data collection. Results revealed that people are connected to each other. They know to each other and their family. Various types of health issues in rural area as headache, joint pain, body pain, viral fever, cough, cancer, heart diseases, depression, piles, autoimmune diseases, blood presser allergy, TV, diabetes, anemia, vitiligo etc.

Key words: Health, Joint pain, piles, wellbeing, viral fever, anemia, diabetes, anemia, vitiligo, depression, autoimmune disease.

Humans have long been curious about and deeply concerned about how the social environment affects both an individual's health and the health of the communities to which they belong. Today, it is evident that social factors have a significant impact on health since unhealthy habits and high-risk behaviors pose the biggest hazards to people's health and wellbeing (Cockerham, 1998: 15). By now, it is widely acknowledged that social and economic variables play a significant role in the multiple causes of disease (Hasan, 1979).

While illness and sick role behavior is the study of how people perceive, interpret, and act in response to illness, health behavior is the study of activities meant to promote positive health and to prevent disease or illness (Weiss, 2000: 5). In contrast to healthy conduct, illness behavior refers to the actions made by a person who becomes unwell in order to identify their condition and find relief from it. Some people identify specific physical signs, such as pain or a high fever, and seek medical help; others who have the same symptoms may try self-medication or disregard them (Cockerham, 98).

Health is defined as "a state of complete physical, mental, and social well-being and not merely the absence of disease or infirmity" in the preamble to the World Health Organization's (W.H.O.) constitution.

Further health is described as an ideal state that is difficult for most people to achieve and does not have any components that are easily countable or measurable, either at the individual or group level. A positive concept, health emphasizes both social and personal resources as well as physical capabilities. It is a resource for daily life rather than the

Statement of the Problem- In the light of above-mentioned framework following questions will be studied-

1. To find out socio economic profile of the sick person.
2. To find out number of diseases in rural area.
3. To know about the family relation, community relation and social relation in the duration of illness behavior.

Overview of Literature:

Medical Sociology-

Medical sociology is concerned with the social causes and effects of health and illness since sociology is an academic field that studies the social factors that influence human conduct. The field of medical sociology applies sociological theories, perspectives, and research techniques to the study of health and medical procedures. The sociology of health services, the social facts of health and illness, the social behavior of health care providers and patients, the social function of health organizations and institutions, and the connections between the systems that deliver health care are all significant areas of research (Cockerham,1997: 01).

A comprehensive definition of the term "health" is frequently elusive; thus, it is probably best re-presented by a variety of definitions, each of which is pertinent to a different political and social cost. "A State of Complete Physical, Mental and Social Well-Being, not merely the absence of disease/infirmity or injury" (WHO, 1946) is the definition given.

1. "Health is the absence of illness."
2. "The nearest approach to health is a physical and mental state fairly free from discomfort and pain, which permits the person concerned to function."
3. "Health is the absence of illness."
4. "The nearest approach to health is a physical and mental state fairly free from discomfort and pain, which permits the person concerned to functions as effectively and as long as possible"

in the environment where chance/choice has placed him" (Dubas, 1978).

5. According to the People's Charter for Health from 2000, "Health is a social and political issue and above all a fundamental human right.

"Illness is a devalued process that affects a person's appearance or functioning and may ultimately result in health." This displays a concern that is undoubtedly not just confined to a person's physical appearance as a member of human communities. varied cultures have varied definitions of an individual's parts, such as their blood, body, social status, spirit, shadow, and name (Cockerham, 1978: 87).

Definitions-

Analysts who focus on issues relating to health and illness use the word "illness" in two different contexts. It can relate to a narrowly defined scientific notion or to any illness that prompts or might prompt someone to pay attention to their symptoms and seek medical attention. Any behaviour connected to an illness is referred to as "illness behaviour."

Williamsom et al. in 1964. They discovered a sizable proportion of serious problems that the doctor was unaware of. As an illustration, "a

third of the respondents with heart disease and a quarter of the respondents with chronic (78).

Area of Study: -

The present study will be conduct at Dabathuwa village. The village is situated Sardhana Road in North-East from Sarurpur block and tehsil Sardhana. The distance of this village 12 Km. far from district Head Quarter Meerut. This village's situated midway from Sardhana & Meerut, total population of this village is 7517 of which 4126 are males while 3391 are females according to censuses 2011. There are all facilities available like Education, Occupation, Medical, Transportation, Communication, Marketing and many more facilities in this village.

Methodology: -

The data for the present study have been collected from 100 respondents for the required fulfillment of the information. The data have been collected through interview schedule/guide. The respondents selected by using the purposive random sampling. Data have been classified with the help of simple statistical & by various tables.

Results and Discussion: -

To find out socio economic profile of the respondent.

Table-1

S/No.	Socio economic profile of respondent	No. of Respondent	Percentage%
1	Age Group of respondents		
	21-40	35	35%
	41-60	45	45%
	61+	20	20%
	Total	100	100%
2	Sex of the respondents		
	Male	40	40%
	Female	60	60%
	Total	100	100%
3	Education of the respondents		
	00-08	31	31%
	09-12	53	53%
	UG-PG	16	16%
	Total	100	100%
4	Marital Status of the respondents		
	Married	80	80%
	Unmarried	09	09%
	Widow	11	11%
	Total	100	100%
5	Family type of the respondents		
	Joint	62	62%
	Nuclear	38	38%
	Total	100	100%
6	Family size of the respondents		
	2-5	45	47%
	6-9	49	47%
	10+	06	06%

	Total	100	100%
7	Family Income of the respondents in thousand		
	00-20	10	10%
	21-40	20	20%
	41-60	29	29%
	61+	41	41%
	Total	100	100%

The above table shows that 45% of the sick persons belongs to 41-60 age group, 60% of female, 80% of respondent belongs to general category, 100% of the respondents are Hindu, 53% respondents are high to intermediate educated 80% joint family, 49% sick persons family size 6-9

persons, 41 family has 60+ thousand income per month.

To Understand about Health Problems/Issues/Diseases in Rural Area is shown in the following Tables: -

Table-2 Health Issues in Rural Area

S/No.	Issues/Diseases	No. of Respondents	Percentage%
1	Allergy	05	03%
2	Anemia	02	02%
3	Autoimmune Diseases	02	02%
4	Back pain/Joint pain	31	32%
5	Blood Pressure	07	07%
6	Cancer	09	09%
7	Cough	04	01%
8	Depression	04	04%
9	Diabetes	01	02%
10	Fever	03	03%
11	Heart Diseases	05	07%
12	Headache	11	11%
13	Piles	02	03%
14	Tuberculosis (TB)	03	03%
15	Thyroid	02	02%
16	Sugar	04	04%
17	Vitiligo (white spot)	03	03%
18	Harpies	02	02%
	Total	100	100%

The results of the above table reveals that the large no. (31%) of the Back Pain & Joint Pain respondents and a smallest no. (01%) Diabetes respondents.

To know about the family relation, community relation and social relation in the duration of illness behavior

Table-3 Social Relations in Community Duration of Illness & Wellbeing: -

S/No.	Behavior of families and Communities with the Respondent	No. of Respondents	Percentage %
1	Good	56	56%
2	Not Good	19	19%
3	Helpful	25	25%
•	Total	100	100%

The results of the above table reveals that the large no. (56%) of the Good Behavior of the Families and Communities with the Respondent and

the smallest no. (19%) of the Not Good Behavior of the Families and Communities with the Respondent.

Findings

Socio-economic profile of the sick persons

1. The study reveals that 45% of the sick persons belongs to 41-60 age group.
2. 60% of the sick persons are female.
3. 80% of the sick persons belongs to general category.
4. 100% of the the sick persons are Hindu.
5. 53% of the sick persons are 9th to 12th educated.
6. 80% of the sick persons are married.
7. 62% of the sick persons belongs to joint family.
8. 49% of the sick persons family size 6-9 persons.
9. 41% family has 61+ thousand income per month.

Health Issues Findings

The results shows that the large no. (32%) of the Back Pain & Joint Pain respondents and a smallest no. (01%) Diabetes respondents.

Social Relations in Community Duration of Illness & Wellbeing

The results of the above table reveals that the large no. (56%) of the Good Behavior of the Families and Communities with the Respondent and the smallest no. (19%) of the Not Good Behavior of the Families and Communities with the Respondent.

Conclusion: -

The study concludes that there is more Health Problems in the Rural Area. Illness behaviors in rural setting. This review is divided into three sections. First, basic terms are defined, socio-economic profile of the sick persons. Second, syndromes characterized by illness behavior are described including somatization, health issues in rural area. Third, methods are social relations in community duration of illness. Results revealed that people are close to each other. They know about each other. various types of health issues and problems in rural area like headache, Blood pressure, joint pain, viral fever, cough, cancer, heart diseases, depression, diabetes, anemia, vitiligo (white spot), piles, autoimmune diseases, allergy, tuberculosis (TB), herpes, etc. In the end study can say that the, rural area people are connected, caring, and helpful to each other in the time period of illness so we can say that rural people are connected and good to take care.

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